

SURVEY FOR NIGHT SHELTERS USERS

Hello. Thank you for participating in this survey. We are a team of University of W researchers and we are interested in your experience during the coronavirus pandemic in Switzerland, since around March 1st, 2020. **Please answer as honestly as possible, because there are no incorrect answers and your data will remain anonymous.**

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary and without remuneration. Likewise, all the data you provide is anonymous and confidential. If you would like to know more about this project, you can contact us by telephone by dialling X or by writing an e-mail to @

0. Have you ever filled this questionnaire in the past ?

- Yes
- No

1.1 Your assigned sex (at birth) is:

- Female
- Male
- Intersex

1.2 You consider yourself as (gender):

- Woman
- Man
- Gender fluid
- Other

2. What is your age? _____

3. Do you have children? No Yes

4. Are you in a relationship or married? No Yes

5. Where do you spend the night? (Multiple replies possible)

- At someone else's home
- At a night shelter
- On the streets
- Other _____

6. You feel:

- Very unhealthy
- Unhealthy
- Neither unhealthy nor healthy
- Healthy
- Very healthy

7. Are you at a higher risk from coronavirus?

- Yes, I have health issues (immunological, respiratory, diabetes, etc.)
- Yes, I am an elderly person (aged 65 or more)
- No

8. How has the pandemic affected your life (since March 1st, 2020)? Select the answer which best applies to you.

Very negative impact	Negative impact	Neither a negative nor a positive impact	Positive impact	Very positive impact
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9. More into detail, since the beginning of the pandemic in Switzerland: (Multiple replies possible)

- I have lost my job and/or had my work hours reduced because of the virus
- I have been furloughed (technically unemployed)
- I had to spend all or a large part of my savings
- I have lost my housing
- My health got worse
- I had to eat less for financial reasons
- I had to stop meeting friends/members of my family for a while
- I have friends/members of my family who have been infected by the coronavirus
- I have friends/members of my family who have died because of the coronavirus
- I have caught the coronavirus

10. During the pandemic, what have been your most important needs? (Answer freely)

11. During the pandemic, you have spent the day, in person:

- Alone
- With strangers
- With friends
- With your significant other
- With family

12. During the pandemic, you have interacted with friends or family from a distance (via social networks, WhatsApp, telephone, SMS, etc.)

- Every or almost everyday
- Several days each week
- Sometimes
- Never
- I do not have either family or close friends

13. Select the answer which best applies to you:

13.1 During the pandemic, I generally felt...

- Very unhappy
- Unhappy
- A bit unhappy
- Neither unhappy nor happy
- A bit happy
- Happy
- Very happy

13.2 During the pandemic, I have been anxious...

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

13.3 During the pandemic, I have been irritated...

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

13.4 During the second wave of the pandemic (from September 2020), you felt:

- Much better than during the first wave (March-August 2020)
- Better than during the first wave (March-August 2020)
- Similar to the first wave (March-August 2020)
- Worse than during the first wave (March-August 2020)
- Much worse than during the first wave (March-August 2020)

14. Compared to before the pandemic, do you consume more or less:

14.1 Tobacco

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- I do not consume

14.2 Alcohol

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- I do not consume

14.3 Drugs (cannabis, cocaine, heroin, etc.):

- Much more
- More
- A bit more
- Neither more nor less
- A bit less
- Less
- Much less
- I do not consume

15. During the pandemic, have you been victim of physical assault and/or theft?

- No (**go to question 17**)
- Yes, of physical assault (**go to question 16**)
- Yes, of theft (**go to question 16**)
- Yes, of both (**go to question 16**)

16.1 During the pandemic, how many times have you been victim of physical assault and/or theft?

- Physical assault: ____ times
- Theft: _____ times

16.2 Where did the physical assault(s) or theft(s) happen? Select all answers that apply.

- On the street
- At a night shelter
- In someone else's home
- Other (specify): _____

16.3 At what time of day did the physical assault(s) or theft(s) happen? Select all answers that apply.

- Around morning (between 6:00 and midday)
- Around afternoon (between midday and 18:00)
- Around evening (between 18:00 and 24:00)
- Around night-time (between 24:00 and 6:00)

16.4 Indicate the approximate date of the assault and / or theft if you remember: _____

17. During the pandemic, have you hit someone and/or stolen something?

- No (**go to question 19**)
- Yes, I hit someone (**go to question 18**)
- Yes, I stole something (**go to question 18**)
- Yes, both (**go to question 18**)

18.1 During the pandemic, how many times have you hit someone and/or stolen something?

- Hit someone: ____ times
- Stolen something: _____ times

18.2 During the pandemic, where did the assault and/or theft happen? Select all answers that apply.

- On the street
- At a night shelter
- In someone else's home
- Other (specify): _____

18.3 During the pandemic, at what time of day did the physical assault(s) or theft(s) happen? Select all answers that apply.

- Around morning (between 6:00 and midday)
- Around afternoon (between midday and 18:00)
- Around evening (between 18:00 and 24:00)
- Around night-time (between 24:00 and 6:00)

18.4 Indicate the approximate date of the assault and / or theft if you remember: _____

19. Currently, how much money, more or less, do you make each month?
_____ Swiss francs

20. Currently, how much cash, more or less, do you have in total? (In your pocket and/or in a bank account): _____ Swiss francs

21. What is the highest level of education you completed?

- I have no education
- Primary school (around 6 years of school completed)
- Middle school (around 9 years of school completed)
- High school or equivalent (around 12 years of school completed)
- University, polytechnic school, or higher education school (Bachelor, Master and/or PhD degree levels)
- Other (specify): _____

22. How long have you been in a homeless situation?

- Before March 2020
- From March 2020

23. If you had a magic wand, what would be the first thing you would do with it? (Answer freely)

24. What is/are your nationality/nationalities? _____

25. What is your residence status? _____

26. Concerning the questionnaire:

- The social worker read the questionnaire to me
- I have filled the questionnaire alone and I asked help to the social worker when needed
- I completed the questionnaire all by myself

27. Use this box if you have additional comments:

Well done, you have finished the questionnaire! Your answers are precious to us and we hope that they will help in better taking care of you in the event of a future crisis. We thank you for your participation.